

User Test 3 – Interview questions

Initial Information

We'll start off with a short interview session to warm up, after which you will spend a couple of minutes interacting and listening to the soundscape with headphones on. Then we'll finish with a final interview about your experience.

Questions Before

- Please state your experiment code.
- How are you feeling?
 - “Would you mind elaborating a bit?”
 - “Could you expand on that?”
- What do you enjoy doing in your freetime?
 - “Why do you enjoy doing those things?”
 - “How come?”
- What thoughts do you have about climate change?
 - “Are we doing enough?”
 - “Is there anything particular that concerns you?”
 - “Why is that?”
 - “What about X makes you think Y?”
- Ok, thank you for that. Now I will read you some instructions and then you'll get to listen.

Prompt before they start listening

You will now spend some time interacting with the soundscape. On the screen you will see a timeline that you are free to explore at your own pace. When selecting a new year, some sounds have a short delay and may need a few seconds to adjust. At some point there will also appear a button that allows you to change the trajectory of greenhouse gas concentration in the atmosphere.

The minimum duration is five minutes, after that you can stop whenever you want or when I tell you it's time.

Exclude for control group: In the previous tests you were asked to listen to the sounds and share your thoughts about how you perceived them. This time, we'd like you to avoid analyzing the sounds too much and instead let the soundscape guide your thoughts.

During this interaction we'd like you to reflect on the potential impacts of climate change on animals, nature and yours and other people's lives here on Earth.

Questions After

- Did your mind wander off in thoughts or do you feel like you were present?
- What did you think about?
 - Why is that?
 - Did you come up with anything?
 - Any thoughts or reflections that appeared while listening?
- What did you feel?
 - Why do you think you felt that way?
 - Why is that?
 - "When you say A, what about it makes it A?"
- **If their answers so far haven't touched on climate change:**
 - Any reflections related to climate change?
- Were there any sounds that...
 - ...caught your attention in particular?
 - ...
 - "Did that thought make you feel any particular way?"
- Do you feel like you got anything out of this experience?
- After participating in this study, do you think that a tool like this could be used to increase an individual's:
 - ...concern for the climate?
 - ...motivation for living more sustainably?